

MEDICAL SCIENCES

ENDODONTIC PREPARATION OF MAXILLARY PREMOLARS

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Abstract

Endodontic treatment methods are constantly being improved, especially in the field of tooth root canal preparation. There has been a progression from stainless steel hand instruments used in conjunction with mechanical dilators to rotary nickel titanium instruments. Despite the variety of materials, modern root canal preparation concepts are no different from those proposed by Dr. Herbert Schilder more than 40 years ago, since any preparation method requires copious irrigation. It is necessary to thoroughly clean the root canal: remove infected tissue and pathogenic microorganisms. In addition, when treating the canal, the doctor must preserve the original trajectory of the canal, apical structures, including the position and diameter of the apical foramen. And finally, create a uniform expansion from the pulp chamber to the apical foramen, which will allow you to better clean the canal and seal it securely, volumetrically and hermetically.

Keywords; root canal treatment, upper premolars.

Insufficient knowledge of the anatomy of each tooth in three projections without taking into account radiological detectable and undetectable signs, as well as age-related changes, can lead to irreparable errors and complications during endodontic treatment. It is the practical implementation of the fundamental principles of endodontics - adherence to the technique and principles of preparation of the crown and root parts of the tooth that determines successful manipulation during the operation of the appropriate instruments and high-quality obturation of the canals at its various levels. The purpose of this work is to improve knowledge and practical skills in the stages of endodontic preparation of upper premolars. It is important to recall that the concept of endodontic preparation, including upper premolars, includes excision of tooth tissue from the enamel surface (coronal) to the apex (root) using appropriate instruments (described in earlier publications). As a rule, coronal preparation of all chewing teeth, including upper premolars, is carried out through the occlusal surface to create access to the pulp chamber and its opening. The first stage of work begins from the middle of the central fissure of the maxillary premolar along the longitudinal axis of the tooth, excising the enamel and dentin with a cone-shaped fissure bur. The second stage is to open the pulp chamber of the upper premolar with a spherical bur, and a feeling of "sinking" should appear. If the secondary and tertiary dentin are well defined, then the pulp cavity of the tooth is located lower than usual and vertically to a depth of about 9 mm. This depth corresponds to the cervical level of the root, below the neck of the tooth, where the bottom of the pulp cavity is located. The roof of the pulp chamber of the tooth is opened in the bucco-palatal direction, followed by amputation of the pulp. At this stage of the work, the direction of movement of the bur should be from the

inside to the outside, being careful to prevent perforation in the furcation area of the maxillary premolars. As a rule, an endodontic probe is used to clarify the localization of the mouths of the buccal and palatal canals in the first premolar or the central one in the second. Also, by probing, the prepared walls of the cavity (coronal and root parts) of the tooth are examined, the limit and directions of the necessary expansion of the cavity are determined. The final expansion of the coronal cavity of the tooth in the bucco-palatal direction is completed with a fissure bur. In general, a well-prepared coronal cavity in the maxillary premolar creates unimpeded access to the root canal orifices, and the external contours will be identical in both young and elderly individuals.

FIRST UPPER PREMOLAR

The main thing that determines the success of endodontic treatment of the first premolar of the upper jaw is a clear knowledge of its anatomical parameters and the characteristics of this tooth in three projections, taking into account age. The buccal projection of the first upper premolar in young individuals has a large pulp chamber and radiographically reflects: the mesio-distal width of the pulp chamber; the presence of two channels and their direction (mostly straight); distal deviation of the tooth from the central axis by 100. These radiographic data (diagnostic image) are necessary before starting the preparation, since two canals are more common, but there may be three. The medial projection of the same tooth is not determined by radiography and is characterized by the following signs: elevated pulp horns; pronounced boundaries of the pulp chamber in the bucco-palatal plane; the presence of two wide roots, each of which has one straight channel; buccal deviation of the tooth from the central axis by 60. These features influence the size, shape and direction of the final preparation. A cross-section of the root canals of the

first upper premolar in young people allows us to evaluate: the cervical level, which is filled with a large volume of pulp with a pronounced extent in the bucco-palatal plane; the middle part is in the form of an oval shape, which, when instrumented, acquires a rounded taper; the apical third is usually round in shape, but it is narrowed along the perimeter and its instrumental processing is limited to the limits of the cementodentinal junction at 0.5–1.0 mm from the radiological apex of the root. Thus, knowledge of the characteristics of the first premolar of the upper jaw, from the position of assessment in three projections, allows the doctor to correctly form the crown part of the tooth in young people in the form of an oval (ovoid) shape, elongated in the bucco-palatal direction with a smooth transition to the mouths of the root canals. However, you should always remember about age-related changes in teeth in three projections, which also affect the final result of treatment. The buccal projection of the first upper premolar in elderly people due to the intensive formation of secondary and tertiary dentin radiographically reflects: a decrease in the volume of the entire pulp (general recession of the pulp and its thread-like shape in the canal); only one channel visible on the radiograph; distal deviation of the tooth from the central axis by 100. The medial projection of the same tooth is not determined radiographically and is characterized by: general recession of the pulp and “flattening” of the pulp chamber in the bucco-palatal plane in the form of a ribbon; one root with parallel canals and one apical foramen; buccal deviation of the tooth from the central axis by 60. When endodontic treatment of the first premolar of the upper jaw in elderly people, it is necessary to take into account: difficulties in finding the mouths of the canals (buccal and palatal); the direction of each channel can only be determined by a well-bending file; for two canals, one apical foramen may not be determined, but each of the canals is processed separately; usually two channels, but a third is possible. The cross-section of the root of the first upper premolar in the elderly, unlike in the young, at the cervical level has a narrow oval shape in the bucco-palatal direction, and the mouths of the canals are located along the edges of the bottom of the tooth cavity; the middle part is round in shape and the apical third is very narrow. In elderly people, taking into account the above signs in three projections of the first premolar of the upper jaw, the finally prepared coronal cavity takes on an ovoid shape and is more open in the bucco-palatal direction, respectively, parallel to the canals located. Such formed access to the root canal makes it possible to carry out high-quality instrumental processing without any difficulties.

SECOND UPPER PREMOLAR

The upper second premolar has its own parameters, presented in table 2, and characteristic features in three projections, taking into account age-related changes. In young people, the buccal projection of the second upper premolar reflects: a significant volume of the pulp chamber, and on the radiograph one can determine the narrow medio-distal width of the pulp; distal deviation of the apical part of the root (in 34% of cases); distal deviation of the tooth from the central axis by

190. These radiographic data are required before starting preparation (diagnostic image). The medial projection of the same tooth shows signs that are not determined by radiography: a pronounced width of the pulp in the bucco-palatal plane of a “ribbon-shaped” shape; the presence of one root with a large single canal; palatal deviation of the tooth from the central axis by 90. Such features, not detectable radiographically, influence the size, shape and direction of the final preparation. A transverse section of the root of the second premolar of the upper jaw in young individuals allows us to evaluate: the cervical level, filled with a significant volume of pulp in the bucco-palatal plane, and right in the center of the bottom of the pulp cavity, the mouth of the root canal; the middle part is oval-shaped; the apical third is usually round in shape, smaller in diameter, limited by the cemento-dentin junction, located 0.5–1.0 mm from the radiographic root apex. Taking into account all of the above, the formed coronal cavity of the second premolar of the upper jaw takes on an ovoid shape with a funnel-shaped extension to the middle part of the canal, and this allows for effective pulpectomy in young individuals. As a rule, structural changes in the tooth occur with age, and the buccal projection in the elderly on an x-ray is characterized by: a decrease in the volume of the entire pulp area (general recession of the pulp and its thread-like shape in the root canal); the ability to detect two channels (in 2% of cases); bayonet-shaped curvature of the roots (20% of cases); distal deviation of the tooth from the central axis by 190. The medial projection of the same tooth, which is not determined on the radiograph, differs in: the bucco-palatal width of the coronal pulp and the ribbon-like shape; high position of the bifurcation; two separated roots at the level of the apical third; palatal deviation of the tooth from the central axis by 90. In the elderly, the transverse section of the root canal of the second premolar of the upper jaw is assessed: at the cervical level - a narrow oval-shaped pulp chamber, continuing deep into the root; at the middle level there is a bayonet-shaped bend, with the mouths of the canal being round in shape; the apical third is smaller in diameter. The degree of bayonet-shaped bending of the root can be gradually reduced in the process of sequential instrumental and mechanical treatment of the root canal. For unimpeded access to the root canal bend, the prepared coronal cavity should be egg-shaped, located medially on the occlusal surface, with a pronounced inclination towards the bayonet-shaped bend. This inclined cavity allows for an unobstructed approach to the bending of the root canals. When performing endodontic interventions in the second premolar of the upper jaw in the elderly, the clinician should: foresee the difficulties of finding the mouths of the root canals and their deep location; the direction of each canal can be identified using flexible files, moving down the wall of the tooth cavity towards the mouth and deep into the canal; To detect a bend in each root canal, a step-by-step examination of three levels of the root canal is necessary; when expanding the canal, the tip of the endodontic instrument, plunging deeper, should be limited to within 0.5–1.0 mm of the radiographic apex.

Conclusions

Summarizing all of the above, for high-quality endodontic preparation of maxillary premolars, good knowledge of the anatomical parameters and distinctive features of each of them in three projections and taking into account age is required.

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